

DIALECTICS OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL VALUES

Boybekova Shahnoza Aliyevna

Qarshi State University

BoybekovaShahnoza86@gmail.com

Annotation: the article analyzes views related to the transformation of family values in the era of globalization. Opinions related to the conflicting effects of globalization on the national value system and its consequences have been cited

Keywords: family, globalization, value, transformation, society, ethics, marriage, ethnoesthetic monasteries, integration.

To date, globalization processes have had time to penetrate into all spheres of society's life and show their significant influence. These are also bringing sensory changes to the system of family, family relationships and values. Globalization processes are determined by the strengthening of integration and cooperation between states and peoples, the emergence of capital and goods, facilities for the free movement of the labor force, the rapid spread of the achievements of Science, the harmonization of various values on a universal basis, the acquisition of a new quality of inter-civilizational dialogue. It should be noted that modern trends have a constructive and destructive effect on the spheres of life in society. The result is a dynamic change in the character of family relationships and values. The family is an important component of society, forming its main core. The formation and development of the family takes place in direct connection with political, economic, social, spiritual relations in the life of society. Changes in the life of society, the lifestyle of people, living and working conditions, norms of national morality, values, religious beliefs also affect the form and content of family relationships. Therefore, the moral, social, axiological criteria of family relations also undergo changes. After all, "...in today's rapidly changing time of conflict, it is difficult to

find answers to many complex questions in social life without deep study of family issues on a scientific basis” [1].

The large-scale reforms carried out in our republic are aimed at ensuring the priority of spiritual factors in all spheres of public life. As a result of the decision of social relations on the basis of democratic values, special importance is attached to the strengthening of the foundations of free civil society in this process, the essence of which is formed by the goals and interests of the National idea: on the one hand, socio-political, economic-spiritual paradigms characteristic of the development of society are being formed, This assumes the development of Family, Family Relations on the basis of national and universal moral values.

Our first president was I.A.Karimov spoke about the role of the family in the life of society as follows: “in the formation and exaltation of the specific spirituality of any nation, undoubtedly, the role and influence of the family is incomparable. Because, the most pure and pure feelings of a person, the first vital understanding and imagination are formed in the bosom of the family in the first goal. It is natural that the spiritual criteria and views that determine the character, nature and worldview of the child – the foundation of such sacred concepts as good and goodness, Highness and kindness, or-nomus and andisha-are decided in a family setting. Therefore, it is precisely the respect for the parents that arises in the family environment, a deep understanding of the lifelong debt duty to them that forms the basis of the qualities of humanity and family relations inherent in any person, the spiritual world of the family” [2], it was said.

The issue of values is controversial and complexity is one of the issues. Values are things, objects, positive ideas, norms, ideals, principles, criteria that are relevant for a person, society, serve to meet their various needs, are aimed at relieving, elevating their lives, improving the social environment and relationships. Therefore, it is applied to show the universal, social moral, cultural-spiritual significance of certain phenomena in reality. Under the influence of social processes, people's views on values change. This is axiomatic reasoning. For example, a person becomes even

more aware of health when he is sick, and the value of peace when there is war. In this respect, it is of urgent importance to maintain family status in a period that is now rapidly changing, developing and transforming.

Humanity has appeared that this problem has been the focus of attention of olimu fuzalo, philosopher and political scientist, educator and mentors at all times. It is curious that on the tombstone of one of the Pharaohs, who lived three and a half thousand years ago, "our youth is stubborn and stubborn, cannot ignore what the elderly say"denies the values of ancestors" [3] the ending also confirms that youth education has become one of the main issues at all stages of the development of mankind.

Values are not a hardened concept. They are a process in action. The trend towards globalization assumes an emphasis on traditions and values, strengthening efforts to preserve it. The factors that are trying to weaken our national values strive on the one hand to devalue our values, lose identity and eat up national needs. The observation of family relationships at the level of everyday life clearly demonstrates the deformation and degradation of self-centered family values. Today, negative cases remain in the family, despite the care and serious support of the state and society. The weakening of the family also leads to a change in the demographic situation in the country.

An unfailing attitude towards family tradition and old age is visible. One of the peculiarities of the Uzbek family is the high status and rank of the elderly and moms, grandparents in the family, who are always honored, they are allowed to leave them in all matters and then followed to start work. It is pleasing to the eye that this characteristic of the Uzbek family, value, is becoming more polished today. No matter how special the upbringing of the family is, it grows and changes, mainly feeding from a single source. This source is a national-cultural heritage. The family is an integral part of this heritage. Each family appears in society and lives within this society, according to which family relations are determined by the existing

social, economic, legal, ideological, spiritual and educational relations in society and continue to improve under their influence. This masla in particular can be seen on the example of false conformism, which is prominent among young people.

References

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. The pillar of family and society, the grace of our lives and the approval of our blind // people is the highest assessment given to our activities. Volume 2. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2018. – B. 464.
2. I.A.Karimov. High spirituality is an invincible force. - Tashkent: Spirituality, 2008. 52-53 P.
3. Taranov P. Encyclopedia visokogo Uma. M., 1999, p.16.